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Abstract: The 2010 Deepwater Horizon (DwH) accident in the Gulf of Mexico has renewed oceanographic interest in point source buoyant convection. The present paper explores the application of modern numerical techniques to study this problem, focussing specifically on the DwH event. The gas/oil/seawater nature of the problem requires a 'multiphase' approach, which is relatively unfamiliar in physical oceanography, although applications are becoming more common. The model is cast in an Eulerian framework and includes feedbacks between the convection and the environment, unlike past oil/gas plume simulations that adopt a semi-passive, Lagrangian approach.

Fully three dimensional (3d) simulations are too computationally demanding for practical multi-day use, so a two-dimensional (2d) radially symmetric model is abstracted from the equations and calibrated to the 3d results. Both the 2d and 3d solutions exhibit the somewhat unexpected result that oil/bubble plumes modelled after the DwH event are strongly affected by rotation and exert a considerable dynamic feedback on the ambient. These are mechanics not typically included in classical oil/gas plume models. The 2d rotating model with DwH-like parameters produces plume characteristics like those observed during the DwH event.

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December 27, 2016

Prof. Will Perrie
Editor, Ocean Modelling
Elesvier Press

Dear Prof. Perrie:

Attached is a revised version of our manuscript OCEMOD-D-16-0017 on 2d-3d multiphase convection model comparisons reviewed previously by Ocean Modelling. The two reviewers made several penetrating comments that we have endeavored to address. Perhaps the most significant issue dealt with the need for more quantitative substance to our model validation and this is addressed at several points in the present revision. Responses to specific comments are included below; please thank both reviewers on our behalf for what was clearly a thorough and thoughtful reading and recommendations that, we believe, have improved our manuscript.

The original reviewers comments appear below in italics and our responses in regular type.

Please contact me should you require any other materials in regards to this revision. Otherwise, we look forward to hearing your editorial decision.

Sincerely,

WK Dewar
Prof of Oceanography

Reviewer 1.

This reviewer is thanked for his/her many penetrating comments and for pointing out relevant references that we were unaware of.

This paper presents numerical solutions for a mixture model of a plume with the inclusion of rotation effects. The work is presented in the context of the Deepwater Horizon accident. The paper is well written, I found the content to be of interest, and view the material as publishable.

The reviewer is thanked for his/her kind words.

There are a number of comparable multi-phase continuum models and the one employed herein is plausible if not unique. I appreciate that the authors have discussed some of the numerical details elsewhere but there are a few places where a more self-contained discussion could have been presented (eg. the computational sponge layers).

Agreed. Specific responses are outlined below.

Some general comments are below:

1. The Morton et al. models of turbulent plumes have recently been shown to be ill-posed when applied directly to unsteady problems, either through unsteady source conditions or via an initial-value problem (Scase and Hewitt, 2012). Alternative models have been put forward for jets (Craske, 2016).

References to Scase and Hewitt and Craske and van Reeuwijk have now been included on line 50. Craske, 2016 deals with jets in a neutral environment and so we prefer to not use this reference.

2. I think the paper would benefit from a little more detailed discussion of the origin and choice of the inter-phase slip velocities.

Perhaps the most thorough studies of gas slip velocities are Simiano (2005) and Socolofsky, et al. (2005). The former concluded a single slip velocity worked well as long as it was representative of the distribution. We have opted for a slip velocity based on the data in Lehr (2010) obtained during DwH and used in Socolofsky (2011). Statements along these lines now appear on or near line 173 in the revision. We recognized the need to explore this further, and make statements to this effect in the Future Work subsection.

3. I'm a little surprised to find rotation effects so visible at $Ro=10$ (e.g figure 3), do the authors have any speculation as to why?

You're surprised? We're surprised. This is one of the points we try to emphasize in our papers on this topic, including the present. We think angular momentum

conservation, which implies swirl speed depends on the inverse of radial distance from the plume, creates sizable flows quickly, after having drawn in relatively nearby fluid. Since no swirl speeds develop in the absence of rotation, this distinction becomes evident very quickly.

4. There is some spatial oscillation visible in figures 3 & 4 ($2D, f_T=f_b=0.5$). Is there any propagating wave behaviour?

As far as we can tell from the numerical solutions, these are steady and so no propagation is present. We have included a statement to this effect.

5. I often found the figures to be somewhat distant from their point of discussion in the text.

We are uncertain of the meaning of this comment as all the figures all appear at the end of the manuscript and so are all far from their point of discussion in the text. As a result, no modification of the paper has been included in reference to this point.

6. Are the 4 sub-figures of figure 10 equally spaced through the oscillation period? Is this in any way related to the presence of inertial-gravity wave mechanics?

The answer to both queries is yes, and we have added statements in the text to this effect. We have also changed the figure to show the oscillation in temperature and angular momentum, as these show the oscillation structure more clearly. We now also include a plot of a passive tracer from this experiment, as it comments on an interesting aspect of oil dispersion.

Minor issues:

1. Page 24. "eraaror"

We have not found this typo in our version.

2. Reference 15 "p;lumes"

Fixed.

Reviewer 2

The reviewer is thanked for his/her penetrating comments that have helped us craft an improved manuscript. Detailed responses appear below.

A. One of my central concerns is that the comparison between the 3d and 2d simulations made in figures 3 and 4 is entirely qualitative and therefore subject to interpretation. Indeed, despite the authors' claim that the 3d dynamics are 'well captured' by the 2d model, my impression is that the agreement between the two models is quite poor. I suspect that if a comparison were made of the volume flux in the plumes, or their widths, (i.e. leading-order integral quantities) that the disparity would be made even more evident. I do not think that it is satisfactory to justify a model's accuracy using qualitative comparisons when it is later to be used to make quantitative predictions (see e.g. figures 5-7, unless I am mistaken).

Have the authors considered comparing the entrainment coefficient as a function of z from the 3d and 2d simulations? The entrainment coefficient is an important parameter that encompasses all of the difficulties of modelling this problem and therefore provides an opportunity to simplify/focus the discussion and analysis.

The original Figs. 5-7 from the original manuscript were in fact from the 3d model, not from the 2d model. This was not made clear in the text and is a point we have dealt with in the revision.

Quantification of the validation is a good suggestion, and the reviewer is thanked for it. We now include several figures that address this point. Specifically, beginning at line 278, we discuss 2d/3d non-rotating comparisons (see Fig. 5 of this version) of vertical velocity, temperature and gas volume fraction. Temperature the near well-head differs between the 2d and 3d results, as was emphasized in the previous version (and also in this version) and discussed as a poor representation of near field entrainment. However, this discrepancy erodes quickly so that by $z=3$, the 2d/3d values and structures all agree well. The 2d/3d non-rotating agreements are otherwise encouraging. We also make similar comparisons for rotating thermal plume cases where the agreement is also encouraging. The rotating hybrid comparison is generally poorer because, as we say in the text at several locations, we are unable to obtain quantitatively accurate results using a Smagorinsky parameterization in the rotating setting.

Fig. 6 includes comparisons of plume width, as indicated by the structure of the vertical velocity field at a given location in the plume, and vertical mass flux as a function of vertical location, to indicate the behavior of integral plume measures. We typically see

the 2d plume is narrower and the mass flux lower than the 3d plume, because of the entrainment discrepancies, but the difference is roughly a factor of 2. The rotating 2d hybrid case again emerges as much poorer in comparison.

The difficulties with the hybrid case also emerge in the next comment.

In addition to the points raised above I am also concerned about the calibration of the 2d model. Precisely how the 2d model was calibrated is not explained, although it would appear that a different calibration must be used to adequately capture rotational effects. The inability of a model to reproduce observations over a range of parameters suggests that something is missing from its representation of the physics. I would like to see a more detailed discussion and analysis of this matter in preference to the calibration of the model on a case by case basis.

The reviewer is thanked for emphasizing what was one of the principle points we wished to make in this paper. Adding rotation makes this convection problem fundamentally different, to the point that we were extremely limited in how well we could calibrate our 2d model to fit the 3d results. The reason for this is, as the reviewer states, physics is missing. In the present case, the missing (or inaccurate) physics is that the source of the turbulence in the rotating case is no longer shear generated turbulence. Rather, buoyant convection dominates the plume, but it is a buoyant convection strongly modified by rotation and with extremely fine scales. We had to eliminate Smagorinsky dissipation on the swirl velocity in order to even obtain qualitative comparisons with the 3d results. This was an ad-hoc move and might not be the only way to improve the comparison, but rather than hunt for a better parameterization, we opted to emphasize the new result about rotation and move forward with the calculations.

As requested by the reviewer, we have added statements to the text to emphasize these points. See comments starting on line 339.

B. Due partly to the problem's complexity and to the different models employed, the reader is left with a rather nebulous impression of how/whether the physics of this problem can be represented in a simple manner. The final sentence in the abstract provides a good example:

'The long-term 2d DwH plume differs importantly from classical non-rotating plumes, however non-rotating and rotating models are comparable in their ability to explain the DwH observations'

We have been told that rotational effects are important, yet, taken at face value, this

sentence appears to suggest that rotational effects are not relevant in simplified models.

The reviewer has pointed out our failure to communicate our point, which is that the available observations from the DwH event are not sufficiently detailed that they can discriminate between hindcasts based on rotating or non-rotating dynamics. Non-rotating models have attempted quantitative tests to see if they can explain the available DwH observations and have obtained some level of success. We can do the same. This is not due to a lack of importance of rotation, it is due to a lack of detailed observations that can discriminate between the two models. This is not a criticism of the DwH field campaign as tracking and monitoring the plume was a difficult job. But we can claim credibility given the available observations at the same level as non-rotating models have done.

We have included statements as needed, and modified the sentence in the abstract to communicate our point more clearly.

In the light of the many questions that appear to remain open relating to the effects of rotation on turbulence in this problem, I was surprised to learn that the authors advocate future work that looks at the effects of an additional source of complication, namely a cross flow.

We agree that an adequate investigation of rotation in this problem has not yet been completed, but from a practical perspective it is also true that cross flows were an important component of the DwH environment. It is an important practical extension of our results to include cross flows in a rotating setting to explore any new modifications arising in this case. We have therefore elected to leave our statements about the importance of future work including cross flows.

53: I question the view that Lagrangian models are the more classical, especially in view of the fact that in citing the early work of Schmidt and Morton, Taylor & Turner, the authors are referring to Eulerian models.

Agreed and our discussion has been modified as suggested.

56: In my opinion the background/literature review, currently consisting of disparate facts/remarks rather than a cohesive story, could be significantly improved. Please try to provide the reader with a coherent overview that motivates subsequent sections.

We have attempted a revision that we hope is satisfactory to the reviewer.

58: Perhaps also consult 'Zeldovich, Y. 1937 The asymptotic laws of freely ascending

convective flows', which predates the cited work by Schmidt.

Reference now cited in line 43. Thanks for pointing this out.

101: Nowhere (as far as I could tell) are we given precise details about the extent to which the 3d simulations are 'turbulence resolving'. Is one to assume that these were direct numerical simulations and that, therefore, the grid was able to capture the smallest (Kolmogorov) scales of the flow?

Instead of an explicit modelling of the subgrid terms using, for instance, a Smagorinsky model, we use here the Spectral Vanishing Viscosity technique. Examples of this procedure for fully-developed channel configurations have shown excellent agreement with Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS). A fuller description of these details is now provided in the text beginning on line 135.

111: I am not entirely convinced that a comparison with heated seawater provides additional insight here.

The reviewer is correct that not much additional insight emerges from this comparison, however there is a rich and long literature on the purely thermal point source plume in both sustained and instantaneous releases. Inasmuch as we find rotation a dominant effect for these cases, we felt some discussion was warranted. In addition, the Helfrich and Battisti laboratory experiments provided some verification of our finding of a convective precession. In view of these points, we have elected to retain the comparisons.

175: Throughout the manuscript (i.e. here and elsewhere) the numerical simulations are referred to as experiments, which is extremely misleading. My assumption is that a "three dimensional experiment" corresponds to a laboratory experiment.

Agreed. We have modified the phraseology as recommended.

194: Given the title of the journal, 'modeled' should probably be changed to 'modelled'.

Agreed and changed.

199: Is one to assume that no-flux conditions correspond to Neumann conditions? The convective flux is non zero I presume?

Yes, 'no-flux' stands for Neumann. Also, the convective flux is, of course, non-zero.

201: Why is a sponge layer used on the side walls rather than the top boundary? What

happens if a sponge layer is not used?

We wanted to damp spurious reflections from the model sidewalls and allow for inflow that reflected neutral far field conditions. We have added some statements to this effect.

205: The units should be s^{-2} .

Agreed and corrected.

212: A widening core does not necessarily imply entrainment. Note that necking plumes also entrain.

True, but entrainment is occurring in these simulations and leads to the widening core. We prefer to leave the sentence as is.

Table 1: Why not also include the parameters for the DwH case?

Now included.

Figure 1: I would consider plotting the different fields in separate windows; the figure is difficult to read in colour and impossible to read in black and white.

The figure is meant only to convey qualitative information about our 3d simulations. We prefer to leave it as it is.

260: ‘...do not expect the system to be inviscid’. What exactly do you mean here? Viscosity is a property of the fluid rather than the system. I assume you are referring to the smallness of the viscous terms in the mean momentum budgets.

This statement refers to our appealing to angular momentum conservation to qualitatively explain our results. Of course, angular momentum will not be perfectly conserved (the system will not behave in an inviscid manner), but this is still a useful interpretational concept. We have modified the sentence to clarify the point. See the discussion after line 231.

276: Do you mean eddy viscosity?

Yes. Sentence changed accordingly.

292: Poor grammar: Rossby numbers don't argue.

Agreed. Sentence modified as requested.

304: To say that the 3d dynamics are well captured by an axisymmetric model needs more explanation and is, based on a qualitative comparison alone, highly questionable in my opinion.

Please see above discussion.

319: Poor grammar; do you mean that the agreement between the 2d and 3d simulations is not good?

Agreed. Sentence modified as requested.

324: From what do you infer that entrainment is suppressed? Suppress means to prevent from happening –is this really what you mean? Is turbulent entrainment really zero? If turbulent entrainment is reduced, which is what I assume you mean, then what might be the cause of this and how does it relate to the model you are using?

According to Merriam-Webster, to ‘suppress’ is to ‘inhibit the growth or development of’, which is what we intended to say with regards to much of the plume development. The reviewer is correct in that the specific instance referred to here refers to a qualitative 2d/3d comparison, and the sense we were attempting to convey was a ‘weakening’ of the entrainment in the 2d results relative to the 3d results. The offending sentence has been changed.

349: Poor grammar.

Agreed and fixed.

406: A more detailed explanation would be helpful.

Agreed and sentences have been added.

694: To refer to A.22 as containing ‘error’ is confusing. Presumably you mean that the term in question is of order 0.1? In addition ‘less justifiable’ is misleading; indeed what is the justification for using the Boussinesq approximation when the relative density differences are around 0.1? Why not attempt to estimate the error associated with the Boussinesq approximation from the governing equations? It would be particularly interesting to know how the rotational effects that you identify as being important would be influenced by the incorporation of non-Boussinesq effects.

The sentence in question is meant to indicate the size of the errors contained in the equations. There isn’t a ‘justification’ for using the Boussinesq approximation other than

the equations are more amenable to numerical implementation and practical study and, are arguably, sufficiently accurate in this multiphase application. That having been said, we feel it important to emphasize where quantitative assumptions are made and to state how large is the error associated with them. The reviewer raises a good point about the combined effects of rotation and any compressive dynamics associated with the multiphase fluid we study. We don't have an answer to the question, but will pursue it in the future. Rewordings of the section in question have been attempted which we hope clarify its meaning.

There are many instances in the manuscript where the grammar and clarity of discussion could be improved significantly. I urge the authors to think carefully about how to focus and refine their discussions to provide a more coherent and rigorous account of their observations and insights.

The reviewer has indeed motivated us to rethink our presentation and is thanked for that. As an example of our refinement, the figures in this version have been reworking thoroughly to more clearly convey our message. We hope the result contained in this version of the paper will be satisfactory.

Highlights

Multiphase rotating convection
2d/3d comparisons
turbulence resolving models
Deep Water Horizon

¹ **Rotating 2d Point Source Plume Models with**
² **Application to Deep Water Horizon**

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Key Points.

Multi-phase plumes with rotation, 2-D/3-D comparisons

3 **Abstract.** The 2010 Deepwater Horizon (DwH) accident in the Gulf of
4 Mexico has renewed oceanographic interest in point source buoyant convec-
5 tion. The present paper explores the application of modern numerical tech-
6 niques to study this problem, focussing specifically on the DwH event. The
7 gas/oil/seawater nature of the problem requires a 'multiphase' approach, which
8 is relatively unfamiliar in physical oceanography, although applications are
9 becoming more common. The model is cast in an Eulerian framework and
10 includes feedbacks between the convection and the environment, unlike past
11 oil/gas plume simulations that adopt a semi-passive, Lagrangian approach.
12 Fully three dimensional (3d) simulations are too computationally demand-
13 ing for practical multi-day use, so a two-dimensional (2d) radially symmet-
14 ric model is abstracted from the equations and calibrated to the 3d results.
15 Both the 2d and 3d solutions exhibit the somewhat unexpected result that
16 oil/bubble plumes modelled after the DwH event are strongly affected by ro-
17 tation and exert a considerable dynamic feedback on the ambient. These are
18 mechanics not typically included in classical oil/gas plume models. The 2d
19 rotating model with DwH-like parameters produces plume characteristics like
20 those observed during the DwH event.

1. Introduction

21 At 9:45PM, April 20, 2010, an explosion occurred on the Deep Water Horizon drilling
22 rig, located in the Gulf of Mexico, killing 11 people and injuring 17 others (*Graham et al.*
23 [2011]). This was the beginning of the Deep Water Horizon accident, an event that lasted
24 for 87 days. The spill went through several phases: the initial phase where the deep pipe
25 leaked from two locations, the phase where the riser pipe was cut, localizing the spill
26 to the wellhead and last, additions of various diffusers and dispersants at the wellhead
27 (*Plume Modeling Team* [2010]). The effluent was a mixture of so-called 'Macondo Oil'
28 and gases (primarily methane). The oil, itself a mixture of several different hydrocarbons
29 (*Reddy et al.* [2012]), constitutes an independent material from the water and is largely
30 immiscible with it. The gas is also an independent phase but is more likely to be consumed
31 and to dissolve into the seawater. The discharge was large (4.9 million barrels of oil and
32 about 5.3 million barrels of gas, *Lehr et al.* [2010]) and considerable effort went into oil
33 recovery, burning of surface oil and clean up of beaches dirtied by oil.

34 If recent history is a guide, deep-ocean oil drilling efforts will increase. Taking the above
35 parameters as representative of an 'average' spill, an accident is a major event. There
36 is thus interest in understanding the biological, chemical and physical fate of the oil, its
37 spreading and its impact on the environment. This paper describes and analyzes a some-
38 what novel approach to near-field deep ocean oil plume modelling based on an Eulerian
39 representation that, while more computationally demanding, promises some advantages
40 relative to the more classical Lagrangian based models. A separate and more practical

41 advantage is this design fits seamlessly within existing ocean general circulation models
42 that will support any future oil spill tracking.

1.1. Background

43 Buoyant, turbulent plumes have a literature spanning several decades. *Zeldovich* [1992]
44 and *Schmidt* [1941] conducted early dimensional analyses yielding scaling laws for various
45 plume measures. *Batchelor* [1954], *Morton et al.* [1956] and Turner in a series of papers
46 (see *Turner* [1973] and references therein) performed several analytical and laboratory
47 plume studies. Observations and numerical work on plumes were combined in *Zaker et al.*
48 [2001] and stratified plume experimental results appear in *List and Imberger* [1973]. Well-
49 posed extensions of the *Morton et al.* [1956] models to unsteady settings have recently
50 been advanced by *Scase and Hewitt* [2012] and *Craske and van Reeuwijk* [2016]. A series of
51 scaling laws describing plumes in the presence of rotation and stratification were developed
52 by *Speer and Marshall* [1995], who were motivated by deep ocean thermal vents. The
53 observations by *D'Asaro et al.* [1994] are consistent with much of the scaling, as argued
54 by *Woods and Bush* [1999].

55 *McDougall* [1978] performed early bubble plume experiments and emphasized their
56 effect on neutral level intrusions. *Asaeda and Imberger* [1993] classified two-phase plumes
57 into three types depending upon the number of spreading levels and the strength of the
58 bubble flux (see also *Lemckert and Imberger* [1993]). *Socolofsky and Adams* [2002] and
59 *Socolofsky and Adams* [2005] present more recent non-rotating laboratory bubble plume
60 experiments, emphasizing the importance of constituent slip velocities.

61 Long term rotational plume effects were investigated experimentally by *Helfrich and*
62 *Battisti* [1991] who ran a series of buoyant release experiments at various Rossby num-

63 bers. The numerical plume simulations in *Speer and Marshall* [1995] identified a strong
64 cyclonic circulation at the plume base and a much weaker anticyclonic current at the
65 lateral intrusion, both of which appeared in the *Helfrich and Battisti* [1991] experiments.
66 Momentum and energy budget analysis of turbulent resolving simulations in *Fabregat et al.*
67 [2016a] explained other rotation effects observed in *Helfrich and Battisti* [1991], including
68 a decrease in trapping height and an increase in lateral intrusion thickness.

69 Multiphase plume modelling has historically adopted a Lagrangian approach, meaning
70 particles representing oil droplets and gas bubbles are tracked in a moving environment.
71 Two such models that have been tested against field experiments are the Comprehensive
72 Deepwater Oil and Gas model (CDOG, *Zheng et al.* [2003]) and DeepBlow (*Johansen*
73 [2000]). A second Lagrangian type approach has been to compute the trajectory of integral
74 plume measures, e.g. the centerline location and the plume width. *Socolofsky et al.* [2011]
75 applies simple models of this type to the DwH event focussing on the importance of the
76 regional stratification. A generalized two-phase integral model was developed in *Socolofsky*
77 *et al.* [2008]. *Socolofsky et al.* [2015] describes an intercomparison study between this and
78 several models of the above types as applied to the DwH event. They also describe the
79 participant models in detail.

80 Convection with more than two phases has received less laboratory attention due
81 to the rapidly increasing complexity associated with the staging. However, numer-
82 ical tools for studying multiphase fluids have now been developed (ANSYS Fluent,
83 <http://www.ansys.com>; Foam, <http://foamcfv.org>) and have seen much use in the in-
84 dustrial sector.

85 A turbulence resolving model similar to the one used here (described in the next section)
 86 was recently applied to plumes in a thermally stratified environment and forced either by
 87 heat, gas or a combination of heat and gas (*Fabregat et al.* [2015], *Fabregat et al.* [2016a],
 88 *Fabregat et al.* [2016b]). The overall plume topology dependence on the gas phase slip
 89 velocity observed in the *Socolofsky and Adams* [2002] and *Socolofsky and Adams* [2005]
 90 experiments was successfully reproduced in these simulations. Both rotating and non-
 91 rotating settings were examined. They argued that rotating multiphase plumes differed
 92 significantly from non-rotating ones in several ways, including effects on the turbulence
 93 and precession of the plume axis.

1.2. The DwH Event in Context

Oil and gas are both buoyant in seawater. While Macondo oil density estimates at 1500m
 vary, from a low of $670\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ (Plume Calculation Team, 2010) to $840\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ (Liu, et al.,
 2012; *Socolofsky et al.* [2011]), it is clearly light relative to the $1035\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ seawater density
 of the ambient. Methane density at these pressures and temperatures is roughly $100\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$
 (<http://yeroc.us/calculators/gas-density.php>). Thus, the buoyancy fluxes at the DwH
 wellhead are by oceanographic measures astounding. The oil-gas mixture (approximately
 half oil and half gas) exited the well at roughly $2\text{m}/\text{s}$ (*Plume Modeling Team* [2010]).
 Considering only the oil, allowing for its density anomaly relative to seawater (using the
 larger oil density quoted above), the DwH buoyancy flux was $B_f = 2\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-3}$. As a yardstick
 for evaluating this flux, to produce it with seawater would require

$$\frac{\rho_o B_f C_p}{g\gamma} = \frac{10^3 \text{Kg}}{\text{m}^3} \frac{2\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^{-3}} \frac{4 \times 10^3 \text{J}}{\text{Kg K}} \frac{\text{s}^2}{10\text{m}} \frac{\text{K}}{2 \times 10^{-4}} = 4 \times 10^9 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2} \quad (1)$$

94 4GW m^{-2} ($1\text{GW}=10^9\text{W}$; we ignore that under these circumstances the equation of state
95 would break down), where C_p is seawater heat capacity, g gravity and γ the coefficient
96 of thermal expansion for water. The largest buoyancy fluxes associated with cold air
97 outbreaks over the Gulf Stream are 1000W m^{-2} (*Joyce and Stalcup* [1985]) and last for
98 a few hours, as compared to the 87 day DwH event. The DwH flux is large even in
99 comparison to hydrothermal vents, which are 100-1000 times weaker (*Speer and Marshall*
100 [1995]). Allowing for the methane in the plume, net buoyancy flux increases by a factor
101 of 6.

1.3. This Paper

102 Our interests are in complementing the above Lagrangian/integral multiphase plume
103 models by exploiting modern computational techniques. We develop an Eulerian based
104 multiphase near-field model including explicit turbulence representation. The associated
105 fluid dynamics are very general, thereby allowing for rotation, feedback of the plume on
106 the environment and an evolving background environment. Their design also allows for
107 straightforward inclusion in existing general circulation models.

108 The need for detailed oil evolution is clear particularly given that much (15% to 30%) of
109 the DwH oil remained subsurface (*Lubchenco et al.* [2012]; *McNutt et al.* [2012]). Knowl-
110 edge of how and where in the water column the oil detains and its long term fate is
111 important to assessing subsurface oil ecosystem impacts. It is hoped the present model
112 will be the foundation for a next-generation end-to-end oil spill assessment tool.

113 The next section presents our model in the form of partial differential equations. These
114 are abstracted from discrete statements obtained through a volume integration approach
115 to multiphase fluid dynamics. The derivation of the discrete set is given in the Appendix,

116 along with a brief discussion of the parameterizations necessary to arrive at the continuous
 117 model. We compare two-dimensional (2d) and three-dimensional (3d) models based on
 118 these equations for the purpose of validating the 2d model. The tuned 2d model is then
 119 used to estimate the long-term, multi-day structure of the DwH plume. We conclude with
 120 a summary and future work discussion.

2. Multiphase Equations and Simulations

The equations for a three-phase (oil, gas, water) fluid in a rotating, stratified setting are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} &= -\nabla p + B\mathbf{k} + \nabla \cdot \nu^{visc} \nabla \mathbf{u} \\
 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} T + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} T &= F^T \\
 \alpha_{oil} + \alpha_{water} &= 1 \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_{oil}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{oil} \alpha_{oil} &= F^{\alpha_{oil}} \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (M_{gas}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{gas} M_{gas} &= F^{M_{gas}} \\
 w_g &= w + w_{s,gas} \\
 w_{oil} &= w + w_{s,oil}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

121 and are the equations examined in turbulence resolving calculations by *Fabregat et al.*
 122 [2015] and *Fabregat et al.* [2016b].

123 A complete derivation of (2) is provided in the Appendix. The quantity $\mathbf{u} = (u, v, w)$ is
 124 a mixture velocity formed from the volume weighted average of the oil velocity \mathbf{u}_{oil} and
 125 the seawater velocity \mathbf{u}_{water} . The quantities α_{oil} , α_{gas} and α_{water} are the volume fractions
 126 of oil, gas and water, respectively, T temperature, M_g is the mass of methane per unit

127 volume and p is dynamic pressure. The quantities F^X are flux divergences of quantity X .
128 All constituents are assumed to slip relative to the mixture at the (vertical) speed of $w_{s,X}$
129 where X is the relevant constituent. Oil and water are both taken as Boussinesq and their
130 reference densities are assumed close enough that the mixture can also be considered as
131 Boussinesq. Perhaps the most significant approximation is that gas is considered as dilute,
132 i.e. that its concentrations are low enough that it doesn't significantly affect fluid volume.
133 This appears explicitly in (2d). The buoyancy variable, B , is composed of contributions
134 from all phases, the formula for which appears below.

135 Inasmuch as we use solutions of (2) as truth standards, we now discuss the sense in
136 which these calculations are turbulence resolving. The model is based in the Spectral
137 Element Method (SEM) code Nek5000 *Fischer et al.* [2008b]. Instead of explicit mod-
138 elling of the subgrid terms using, for instance, a Smagorinsky eddy diffusivity (*Özgökmen*
139 *et al.* [2009a, b]), we use the Spectral Vanishing Viscosity technique (*Karamanos and*
140 *Karniadakis* [2000]) consisting of progressively filtering the near-grid scale coefficients
141 in the spectral polynomial expansion (*Fischer and Mullen* [2001], *Deville et al.* [2002]).
142 This approach is similar to increasing the nominal Reynolds and Péclet numbers only
143 at the near-grid scales. Specifically, we used a 5% polynomial filtering of the two high-
144 est modes in the Legendre expansion for all the fields. With this, we ensure stability
145 and preserve the exponential convergence of the solver while avoiding the computational
146 cost associated with computing the sub-grid scale terms. Applications of this procedure
147 to fully-developed, turbulent channel flows have shown excellent agreement with Direct
148 Numerical Simulations (DNS), relative insensitivity to the filter specifics and overall com-
149 putational efficiency (*Koal et al.* [2012]). A turbulent spectrum for a rotating plume using

150 this approach with resolution similar to that used in the present paper appears in *Fabregat*
151 *et al.* [2016c].

152 There are two objectives for the remainder of this section. (1) First, we examine the
153 general dynamics of a DwH-like plume with a particular interest in the impact of rotation
154 on its development. For this purpose, we have conducted a turbulence resolving three
155 dimensional simulation that due to computational overhead extends only for several hours.
156 However, we argue that the importance of rotation is clear by that time. To achieve a
157 statistically steady solution requires modelling for several rotational periods (equivalent to
158 several days of model time). We are thus motivated to develop a computationally efficient
159 two-dimensional version of the model representing the azimuthally averaged evolution of
160 the system. This leads to our second objective, namely: (2) the assessment of our radially
161 symmetric model relative to full three dimensional solutions. We argue below that radially
162 symmetric models can qualitatively capture purely thermal plume dynamics. Quantitative
163 skill in bubble free, radially symmetric, rotating thermal plume models can be achieved
164 but requires somewhat more careful tuning of turbulence parameterizations than it does in
165 non-rotating settings. The inclusion of bubbles in both rotating and non-rotating settings
166 erodes the quantitative accuracy of 2d models to the point that we have been unable to
167 produce an acceptable 2d rotating bubble plume model.

2.1. A Three-Dimensional Simulation

168 We have implemented (2) within the Nek-5000 model (*Fischer et al.* [2008a]), a flexible
169 Navier-Stokes equations solver using spectral elements. The flow configuration consists of
170 a two-phase plume generated by a sustained injection of buoyant fluid and gas bubbles
171 into a linearly stratified, motionless ambient. Oil is modelled as a light fluid without

172 a slip velocity to reduce computational demands, while gas is a separate phase with its
 173 own constant slip velocity, $w_{s,gas}$. We have adopted $w_{s,gas} = 0.2m/s$ in agreement with
 174 *Socolofsky et al.* [2011] who, in turn, were motivated by *Lehr et al.* [2010]. Gas slip velocity
 175 is determined largely by bubble size. Any DwH type release will result in a distribution of
 176 bubble sizes and thus a distribution of bubble slip velocities. The validity of using a single
 177 slip velocity (based on an average bubble size) to represent gas effects has been argued in
 178 *Simiano* [2005]. While we adhere to this choice in the present manuscript, future plans
 179 call for investigating multiple gas slip velocities.

Mixture buoyancy is computed from

$$B = g\gamma(T - T_o)(1 - \alpha_{oil} - \alpha_{gas}) - g \frac{(M_g - \alpha_{gas}\rho_o) + (\rho_{oil}\alpha_{oil} - \alpha_{oil}\rho_o)}{\rho_o} \quad (3)$$

where γ is the thermal expansion coefficient of seawater, ρ_o a constant reference density midway between water and oil ($\rho_o \approx 900Kg/m^3$), T_o a reference temperature and ρ_{oil} the density of oil. Pressure effects on the densities are not included. The mass of methane (M_g) in (3) will be neglected in the following for computational simplicity. Hence, the buoyancy force driving the plume is due to the lower density of the oil and gas phases and the thermal effects associated with the high temperatures of the injected mixture. (The DwH inoculant entered the seawater at roughly $100^\circ C$ (*Reddy et al.* [2012])). Entrainment of the ambient fluid, stratified in temperature, damps the convection. The inlet buoyancy flux B_o is

$$\begin{aligned} B_o &= w_0 AB(z=0) \\ &= gw_0 A \left(\gamma(T(z=0) - T_o)(1 - \alpha_{oil,o} - \alpha_{gas,o}) + \alpha_{g,o} + \alpha_{oil}(1 - \frac{\rho_{oil}}{\rho_o}) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

180 where the inlet is of cross-sectional area A . The notation X_o denotes the inlet value of
181 X . Gas vents to the atmosphere at the slip velocity, but other materials obey a no-flux
182 boundary condition.

183 An example 3d plume generated by our model appears in Fig. 1, where the parameters
184 represent a DwH-like setting. A full analysis of this run appears in *Fabregat et al.* [2015], to
185 which the reader is referred for further detail. Of relevance to this discussion, stratification
186 was set to $N^2 = 2 \times 10^{-5} s^{-2}$, and the net buoyancy flux was $0.4 m^4 s^{-3}$ (the net DwH flux
187 was $1.4 m^4 s^{-3}$ where the buoyancy contributions from gas have been included). Fig. 1 is
188 a snapshot of the turbulent plume 10 hours after initiation. The grey shading represents
189 the 'oil' in this simulation. The three main elements of the plume are: (i) its core from
190 the base to the intrusion level, (ii) the intrusion, or spreading, level where the effective
191 buoyancy anomaly of the plume has been erased by entrainment and (iii) the overshoot
192 region above the intrusion level. The core of the plume widens from the wellhead via
193 turbulent entrainment of the ambient. Part of the entrained cold ambient rises quickly
194 enough that it is negatively buoyant at the spreading level. Above the intrusion, the
195 bubbles keep rising because of their slip velocity. In the core of the plume, it is not only
196 the slip that drives the bubbles, however. The introduction of the gas and the thermal
197 anomaly over the wellhead creates a strong low pressure that draws deep fluid inwards
198 towards the source (see Fig. 2). The inward directed mass flux results in extreme vertical
199 fluid velocities near the plume during its early evolution. These are generally in excess of
200 $1 m s^{-1}$, which greatly exceeds the model inlet velocity.

The maximum rise height in Fig. 1 is roughly 250m and large compared to the classical prediction of *Morton et al.* [1956]

$$h_T = 4.2B_0^{1/4}N^{-3/4} \approx 194m \quad (5)$$

201 for a buoyant plume, where the multiplicative factor 4.2 has been calibrated from experi-
202 ments. The plume state at 10 hours is not yet in equilibrium, however.

203 Rotation emerges as a surprisingly strong effect in this simulation, appearing primarily
204 in the mean cyclonic swirl flows $O(0.1m/s)$ near the wellhead (Fig. 2). In non-rotating
205 simulations, a swirl velocity failed to appear. The cause of the azimuthal flow can be
206 traced to angular momentum conservation which results in a cyclonic flow as distant fluid
207 is drawn to the source. We also find the instantaneous plume structure is generally not
208 radially symmetric, and exhibits a precession around the well head. This appears in Fig.
209 1 in the slant of the plume away from the vertical. Time averaging the precession will
210 lead to a radially symmetric average structure, however the final shape of the plume will
211 be influenced by its presence.

212 The time scale for establishing a statistical steady state in a rotating system is related
213 to the Coriolis parameter and thus typically a few days. Full three dimensional turbulence
214 resolving Nek5000 integrations of this length for DwH parameters are too demanding to
215 be practical (the computation in Fig. 1 required several days of wall clock time). This is
216 a major motivation to examine 2d models, which are considerably more computationally
217 economical. Of course, they require parameterization of the 3d plume turbulence and
218 also suffer from an explicit exclusion of crossflows. Relative to the latter point, integral
219 models which include crossflows often assume circular symmetry about the plume axis, so
220 migrating lessons learned from 2d models to plumes in cross flows remains a possibility

221 here. To address the question of parameterization, we have moved our 3d simulations from
 222 the DwH parameter setting to a parameter regime where computing for several rotation
 223 periods is more feasible. These then provide us with a truth standard to which we can
 224 calibrate the 2d model, as discussed in the next subsection. It is in this exercise that we
 225 have found turbulence parameterization in rotating plume settings is a non-trivial affair,
 226 and is worsened with the inclusion of bubbles. Quantitative agreement between 2d and
 227 3d models is possible for oil/water flows, but is degraded by a phase with a slip-velocity
 228 (like methane).

2.2. A Radially Symmetric Model

Neglecting the non-vertical Coriolis parameter \tilde{f} and azimuthally averaging (2) returns an equation set that is azimuthally independent

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial r} + W \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial z} + \frac{V}{r} \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{U} + f \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{U} &= -\nabla p + B \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{D}_U & (6) \\ \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial r} + W \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial z} &= D_\tau \\ \frac{\partial r U}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial r W}{\partial z} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

229 The quantities $\mathbf{U} = (U, V, W)$ are the averaged radial (r), azimuthal and vertical (z) ve-
 230 locities, respectively. The quantity τ represents any of the tracers T , α_g or α_{oil} . Buoyancy
 231 B is defined in (3) and other notation is standard.

Note, in an inviscid fluid, the azimuthal momentum equation reduces to Lagrangian conservation of angular momentum, λ

$$\lambda = rV + \frac{fr^2}{2} \quad (7)$$

232 Our mixture is not inviscid and thus not exactly conservative of angular momentum,
 233 but the behavior of the DwH model in Fig. 1 suggests angular momentum conservation
 234 strongly affects early plume development.

235 The system (6) proved to be quite computationally economical. Computing several
 236 rotation periods with them required one day on a single processor, while comparable length
 237 calculations with the 3d model required roughly a week when run on ~ 800 processors.

The dissipative terms in Eqs. (6), where turbulence closures will be employed, represent the effects of the residuals emerging from the azimuthal averaging, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_U &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial r \overline{U'U'}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \overline{U'W'}}{\partial z} - \frac{\overline{V'V'}}{r} \\
 D_V &= \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial r^2 \overline{U'V'}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \overline{V'W'}}{\partial z} \\
 D_W &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial r \overline{U'W'}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \overline{W'W'}}{\partial z} \\
 D_\tau &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial r \overline{U'\tau'}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \overline{W'\tau'}}{\partial z}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

238 where the primes denote the residuals and the overbar the averaging.

In the early plume models of *Morton et al.* [1956], radial profiles of all variables were assumed to be Gaussian, thus simplifying (6). Turbulence was parameterized using a simple entrainment hypothesis relating radially inward flow at the plume edge to the core plume vertical velocity. Here for the study of rotating systems we have elected not to employ this assumption. Rather, we adopted a Smagorinsky closure [*Smagorinsky*, 1963] for which the eddy viscosity coefficient ν becomes a function of the vorticity and strain in the flow field

$$\nu = l_s^2 S + \nu_0, \tag{9}$$

with ν_0 a background kinematic viscosity, and S the deformation given by

$$S^2 = 2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{U}{r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] + \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial r} - \frac{V}{r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial z} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

239 The quantity l_s is the Smagorinsky length scale, usually related to the grid size. In
 240 the present case, $l_s = .012m$ (*Rotunno and Emanuel* [1987], *Deremble* [2016]). This
 241 parameterization automatically adjusts to the state of the flow, thus providing a spatially
 242 variable eddy viscosity coefficient.

243 2.2.1. 2D-3D Comparison

244 We have analyzed 4 different model deployments differing in rotation and the compo-
 245 sition of the inlet buoyancy flux (either as a pure thermal buoyancy flux, or as a hybrid
 246 gas/thermal buoyancy flux). All other model parameters were common amongst the vari-
 247 ous simulations (see Table 1). Net buoyancy flux was the same for both the pure thermal
 248 and hybrid cases, and the rotating simulations were characterized by an effective Rossby
 249 number $Ro = N/f$. Stratification in the DwH region varied with depth, from a minimum
 250 of $N = 4 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ to $N = 2.7 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$, and the site was located at a latitude of roughly
 251 $28^\circ N$ (*Socolofsky et al.* [2011]). Thus the Rossby numbers ranged from $Ro \approx 11 - 40$.
 252 Note, Rossby numbers in this range would normally lead to the neglect of rotation.

253 Several equilibrated plumes are compared in Figs. 3 and 4. The thermal plumes are
 254 denoted by $f_T = 1$ (left hand side) while hybrid plumes composed equally of thermal
 255 and gas components are denoted by $f_T = f_b = 0.5$ (right hand side). The top row are
 256 non-rotating cases and the bottom row are rotating examples.

257 The non-rotating thermal plume corresponds to a classic *Morton* [1957] case (see Fig.
 258 3, upper left). The mean structure of the 3d model exhibits a 'classic' shape with intense
 259 vertical velocities at the center, an overshoot and a lateral penetration at the intrusion

260 level appearing most clearly in radial velocity (Fig. 4, upper left). The 3d dynamics are
261 well represented in a qualitative sense by the axisymmetric model with a straightforward
262 implementation of the Smagorinsky parameterization. Maximum values for w are similar
263 between 2d and 3d cases, as are their spatial distributions. In both the 2d and 3d cases, the
264 plume exhibits an overshoot. The 3d radial velocity profile is reasonably well represented
265 in the pure thermal case by the 2d model, although the strength of the 2d outflow is
266 weaker. The maximum extent of the overshoot and the depth of the intrusion compare
267 reasonably well.

268 From the visual comparison of the radial profiles, the inclusion of bubbles has clearly
269 worsened the 2d model performance. The radial flow structure for the hybrid plume,
270 although capturing the overall structure, is weaker in 2d than 3d and intrudes at a much
271 deeper level.

272 The entrainment at the base of the non-rotating plume appears to be the most dy-
273 namically significant distinction between the 2d and 3d models. As can be seen in the
274 radial velocity profiles, entrainment in the 3d case (indicated by negative radial velocities)
275 occurs at the edge of the plume from the bottom to the intrusion level. In the 2d case, a
276 more intense entrainment occurs at the base of the plume, and little entrainment occurs
277 up to the spreading layer.

278 Quantitative comparisons of centerline vertical velocity, temperature and gas volume
279 fraction from the 2d and 3d non-rotating results appear in Fig. 5. Both non-rotating
280 vertical velocity and gas volume fraction are accurately portrayed by the non-rotating
281 2d results. Temperature in the 2d model departs somewhat from that of the 3d profile
282 near the well-head. This is the result of the overly strong entrainment near the domain

283 bottom in the 2d model which floods the plume with cold ambient water. However, by
284 $z = 2$ (approximately six well head diameters), the difference has largely been eroded
285 and the agreement of the remaining structure up the water column is quite reasonable.
286 Comparisons of this sort characterize all the plume variables in non-rotating settings.

287 The inclusion of rotation modifies the equilibrated plume considerably, even at this
288 large Rossby number. Perhaps the most obvious effect is the weakening of the vertical
289 velocities in the purely thermal case (see Fig. 3, lower left). In fact the plume penetrates
290 sideways in the water column as indicated by the strong outward radial velocity (see Fig.
291 4, lower left). Plots of the 3d mean vertical velocity along the plume axis appear in Fig. 5
292 (top right) and serve to illustrate how strongly updrafts over the well-head are suppressed
293 by rotation. By $z = 0.5$ (approximate two well-head diameters), vertical velocities for
294 both rotating thermal and rotating hybrid plumes have effectively vanished. One must
295 be approximately ten times further up the water column to find updrafts this weak in
296 the non-rotating setting. The pure thermal plume even exhibits weak downdrafts on the
297 centerline above $z = 1$. The vertical velocity from the 2d model also appears in this figure;
298 it is discussed further below.

299 As shown in *Fabregat et al.* [2016a], the weak vertical velocities and plume deflection
300 are due to an adverse dynamical pressure gradient on the central axis which balances the
301 buoyancy forces. By effectively pushing down on the wellhead, the pressure field prevents
302 the direct ascension of the buoyant fluid. Instead, the fluid ejects from the wellhead region
303 radially which severely reduces the plume vertical penetration along the central axis. The
304 structure of the dynamical fields reflects the presence of rotation (*Fabregat et al.* [2016b]).

305 To reproduce this in the 2d model of a rotating pure thermal plume, it was necessary
306 to adjust the Smagorinsky parameterization. The examples appearing in Figs. 3 (bottom
307 left) and 4 (bottom left) were obtained by eliminating the Smagorinsky viscosity acting on
308 the swirl speed, leaving only the background viscosity. Other elements of the parameteri-
309 zation were left untouched. The very sharp swirl velocity front the 3d model develops near
310 the wellhead, as a consequence of angular momentum conservation, generates very strong
311 shears and strains that the Smagorinsky model overdamped. Without this adjustment,
312 the 2d model failed to exhibit the off-axis updraft of the 3d results. With the modification,
313 the amplitude and spatial distributions of both the vertical and horizontal velocities in the
314 purely thermal plume were represented well qualitatively and exhibited some quantitative
315 agreement. The 2d rotating thermal plume vertical velocity is compared to the 3d result
316 in Fig. 5 upper right. The suppression of updrafting is evident and downdrafts on the
317 centerline also occur but are somewhat exaggerated in size.

318 Warm temperatures persist well up the axis in the non-rotating results for both cases
319 but are largely confined to the well head area when rotation is included. Further up
320 the column, the 3d temperature reverts to the background temperature for both rotating
321 cases. This also appears in the 2d rotating thermal case, but the inclusion of bubbles
322 yields 2d results departing noticeably from the 3d results, particularly further up the
323 water column.

324 The largest 3d gas fraction concentrations are near the wellhead in the rotating case;
325 but then drop quickly in value to a nearly constant concentration (see Fig. 5). The non-
326 rotating gas distribution penetrates much more effectively into the water column than

327 for the rotating plume, but both converge to small values near the domain top because
328 bubbles dominate the far field behavior for both cases.

329 The inclusion of bubbles again degraded the 2d/3d comparison for the rotating plumes.
330 The bubble effect on the 3d simulation was strong, with the plume exhibiting upward
331 directed flows everywhere along its central axis, in contrast to the pure thermal case.
332 However, the amplitude of the updrafts was quite weak relative to the non-rotating case.
333 This reduction of w was partly captured by the 2d hybrid model, but its spatial distribu-
334 tion was quite different. Downdrafts for the hybrid case outside of the main plume were
335 seen in both the 2d/3d models around heights of $z \sim 3$ (see Fig. 3, lower right). Even
336 with bubbles, the plume was directed off-axis, as seen in the radial velocities from the 3d
337 run (Fig. 4, lower right). There are hints of off-axis structure in the 2d bubble run, but
338 its signature in radial velocities was quite weak.

339 Quantitative comparisons between the 2d and 3d models in plume width and mass flux
340 appear in Fig. 6. Plots of the vertical velocity profile at $z = 3$ appear on the left for all
341 four plume types. The 2d thermal plume is a bit weaker in vertical velocity than the 3d
342 plume, although the radial structure matches well, with downdrafts appearing off-axis.
343 The 2d width is therefore somewhat smaller than the 3d case. A comparable comparison
344 in width occurs for the non-rotating hybrid plume but a somewhat better match in flow
345 strength is seen. A downdraft on the axis still exists at $z = 3$ for the 2d rotating model
346 but is absent for the 3d case, reflecting the somewhat weaker suppression of the plume
347 by the 2d model. The absence of any vertical flow at this depth occurs in both models
348 beyond $r = 0.5$. The rotating hybrid plume vertical velocity at $z = 3$ compares somewhat
349 better than would be expected from Fig. 3; amplitudes are well represented as is the

350 overall structure. Clearly, however, the plume width much smaller in the 2d model than
351 the 3d model.

352 The mass flux in the various models as a function of plume height appears on the right
353 hand side. Similar statements can be made here as were made for vertical velocity. The 2d
354 model tends to underestimate flux in both updrafting and downdrafting zones but similar
355 structure is seen. The rotating hybrid case exhibits the least satisfactory comparisons. In
356 summary, the 2d model captures much of the 3d results qualitatively. Quantitatively, the
357 2d model is overly weak compared to the 3d case but still agrees in orders of magnitude for
358 thermal and non-rotating hybrid plumes. No real skill can be claimed for the 2d hybrid
359 plume model.

360 Clearly there are subtle aspects of the rotating plume turbulence which are difficult
361 to handle quantitatively within the Smagorinsky framework and which are worse with
362 bubbles. The most pronounced differences in the rotating 2d/3d comparisons all occurred
363 in areas where a straightforward Smagorinsky closure in the non-rotating model performed
364 well.

365 A number of robust tendencies emerge from these simulations. First, rotation is a dom-
366 inant effect in these large Ro simulations and is responsible for establishing a cyclonic
367 circulation in the wellhead near field during the early stages of plume development. The
368 momentum is dominated by a cyclogeostrophic balance that blocks the inward directed
369 mass flux, thus stifling the vertical velocity, even to the point that in a purely thermal
370 plume it can be downward. This is quite distinct from the non-rotating system where
371 strong, symmetric, upward convecting plumes always develop. The vertical flow suppres-
372 sion caused by rotation results in the buoyant fluid escaping laterally and at a slant from

373 the wellhead. Our 2d results agree with the azimuthally averaged 3d results on this point,
374 although as argued in *Fabregat et al.* [2015], the slant consists of a precession about the
375 wellhead.

376 Last, there appears to be an effect of rotation on the turbulence near the wellhead.
377 This is inferred from the success in non-rotating systems of the classical Smagorinsky
378 turbulence closure and its lack of success for finite Rossby numbers. The addition of
379 rotation modifies this result significantly, so that parameterization adjustments in the
380 near field were needed. Pure thermal plumes were qualitatively well modeled in this way,
381 but hybrid plumes were not.

382 The importance of rotation is surprising because the Rossby numbers are so large that
383 in classical geophysical fluid dynamics it would be ignored. The key is the geometry of
384 the problem. The symmetry of the plume invokes angular momentum conservation in a
385 radial framework which amplifies the rotational velocities of the background fluid as they
386 draw toward the wellhead.

3. Application to a DwH-Like Event

387 Having assessed the 2d model, we exploit its computational efficiency to examine possi-
388 ble multiple rotation period plume structure for a DwH-like release. We proceed applying
389 our 2d thermal plume model given the quantitative shortcomings of our 2d bubble plume
390 model. Bubbles, however, clearly have a strong effect on the plume so these simulations
391 can only comment qualitatively on the DwH plume.

392 The buoyancy flux in this case was set to $1.3m^4/s^3$, which compares well to the DwH
393 value, including the gas effect. The domain lateral size is $1km$ and its vertical dimension
394 varied from $500m - 1500m$ depending on conditions. For comparative purposes, we com-

395 pute a plume solution in the absence of rotation. When present, rotation was normally
396 $10^{-4}s^{-1}$ and the two buoyancy frequencies $N^2 = 10^{-6}s^{-2}$ and $N^2 = 2 \times 10^{-5}s^{-2}$ were
397 studied, the former being more representative of the DwH site. The resulting Rossby
398 numbers, $N/f = 10, 45$ respectively, bracket that of the DwH site. We also examined the
399 unrealistic rotation rate $f = 4.5 \times 10^{-4}s^{-1}$ in conjunction with the stronger stratification
400 in order to study strong rotation in a more stratified setting.

401 Swirl velocity at the edge of the well head and the vertical velocity at the plume center
402 were monitored until their time series stabilized (about 2 days for both Rossby numbers).
403 The simulations proceeded out to 10 days, without major changes after 2 days in the
404 structure of the fields. Longer periods were not studied because the DwH site was affected
405 by time dependent background flows, and that periods of relative calm, in which one might
406 anticipate a purely 2d model would be useful, were unlikely to last beyond a few days.
407 We focus here on the eventual steady (or statistically steady) states reached by the 2d
408 model.

409 Fig. 7 compares the steady states for $Ro = \infty, 45$ and 10 for the DwH-like settings.
410 The last of these is perhaps the most 'realistic' with regards to the DwH event itself in
411 that the stratification $N = 10^{-3}s^{-1}$ is representative of the area (recall DwH occurred in
412 1500m of water). Note also the vertical scale for the third setting (to 1500m) differs from
413 the prior two. Streamfunction appears on the left and the distribution of a passive scalar
414 on the right. All plots are from 5 days.

The non-rotating plume takes on a very classic structure of an overshoot and plunge
near plume center, followed by a spreading layer. The *Morton et al.* [1956] spreading layer

depth scaling

$$h_T \sim 3.1 \frac{B_o^{1/4}}{N^{3/4}} = \frac{(1.3m^4s^{-3})^{1/4}}{(4.5 \times 10^{-3}s^{-1})^{3/4}} = 190m \quad (11)$$

415 describes the numerical spreading depth quite accurately. The passive scalar tracks an
 416 extended spread out to a distance of at least $1km$. The inclusion of very weak rotation
 417 ($R_o = 45$, Fig. 7, middle) modifies the picture significantly. The previously described
 418 outward slant appears with indications of downdrafts very close to the plume axis. The
 419 spreading layer depth is strongly depressed, here achieving a height of approximately
 420 $125m$, i.e. roughly 60% of that noted in the non-rotating case. There is evidence of a
 421 spreading layer at a height of $250m$ in the passive scalar, but this is a remnant of the
 422 initial adjustment process. Very early in the rotating evolution, the plume penetrates to
 423 heights comparable to those of the non-rotating case. With the development of the swirl
 424 velocity, the plume moves off-axis and retreats to its final spreading height seen in Fig. 7,
 425 where it remains to at least 10 days. Later plots (not shown) indicate an active spreading
 426 layer at $125m$ and an inactive remnant at $250m$.

To move the rotating case more clearly into the DwH regime, the stratification was reduced to $N = 10^{-3}s^{-1}$, the results of which appear in Fig. 7, bottom panel. Once again, the off-axis plume appears and clear indications of downdrafts are seen on the plume axis. With the reduced stratification, plume penetration is much more effective, now reaching a height of roughly $600m$. The active spreading layer is clearly well developed at $600m$ and a remnant of the initial plume development appears around $1300m$. The rotational suppression of the plume at 5 days for this case is roughly $160m$, as the *Morton et al.* [1956] scaling for the maximum plume height predicts

$$h_T \sim 4 \frac{B_o^{1/4}}{N^{3/4}} = \frac{(1.3m^4s^{-3})^{1/4}}{(10^{-3}s^{-1})^{3/4}} = 760m \quad (12)$$

427 Increasing the strength of the rotation by a factor of 4 results in a more effective plume
428 suppression, although the effect is not linear in the Rossby number. A separate interesting
429 result of this experiment (not shown here) is that the plume slowly grows in height for the
430 next several days. This has the effect of broadening the width of the actively spreading
431 plume. What is a roughly 100m thick spreading layer centered at 600 at day 5 becomes
432 a roughly 200m thick layer centered at 750m by day 10.

433 To broaden our parameter regime, we also considered a strongly rotating plume in a
434 strongly stratified setting, using $N = 4.5^{-3}s^{-1}$ and the unrealistic Coriolis parameter
435 $f = 4.5 \times 10^{-4}s^{-1}$, which yields a Rossby number of 10. The early plume evolution for
436 this case resembled that of both previous simulations, showing a rapid development of
437 plume penetration followed by a slower retreat of the plume towards an eventual roughly
438 equilibrated depth of 130m. However, the most unexpected finding from the simulation
439 was the plume did not settle into a steady state. Rather, the depth of maximum plume
440 penetration cycled between two depths approximately 130m apart, from a maximum of
441 200m to a minimum of 75m. The oscillation as illustrated in temperature at 20 minute
442 intervals appears in Fig. 8 and in angular momentum in Fig. 9. It consists of periodic
443 increases and decreases in the height of plume penetration, visible in temperature, and
444 on and off-axis plume excursions, visible in angular momentum. The angular momentum
445 surfaces also show wave like propagation away from the plume, consistent with gravity
446 wave dynamics. The oscillation period is roughly 1.5 hours, which is easily supported as a
447 gravity wave by the stratification (buoyancy period ~ 20 minutes). It is interesting that
448 even though rotation is strengthened by a factor of 4 relative to the strongly stratified re-
449 sults appearing in Fig. 7 middle, the mean plume penetration depth is not much different

450 between them. This reflects the continuing transition of the transient plume between a
451 relative efficiently penetrating on-axis plume state and a suppressed and poorly penetrat-
452 ing off-axis plume state. This both slows and thickens the spread of the passive scalar.
453 As seen in the bottom right plot in Fig. 9, at 5 days, the passive tracer is several hundred
454 meters thick and has spread only to 600m.

455 *Deremble* [2016] in an exploration of the steady solutions of the 2d model equations
456 found regimes of multiple equilibria characterized in his case by an on-axis solution and
457 an off-axis solution. Both solutions were stable for the parameter settings he explored.
458 This invites the interpretation of this last case that for DwH parameters, multiple steady
459 solutions of the equations exist, but are unstable. The oscillation thus represents the
460 approach of the system to one of those states followed by its repulse toward the other
461 state.

4. Discussion

462 We have here introduced and tested a multi-phase model designed for use in the deep
463 ocean. We are motivated by the recent Deep Water Horizon event and the continuing
464 exploration for oil in the ocean. The aims of the derivation were to retain the essential
465 elements of the problem while simplifying the model as possible for economy in compu-
466 tations.

467 We have derived an Eulerian model to more easily interface with ocean general circu-
468 lation models, and it is effectively Boussinesq, in that both oil and water are treated as
469 individually and jointly Boussinesq. The equations, derived in discrete form using an in-
470 tegral approach, make clear the need for inter-volume exchange parameterizations. With

471 relatively intuitive choices for these parameterizations, the equations correspond to the
472 discrete representation of an underlying set of partial differential equations.

473 We have calibrated and applied the model to DwH-like buoyant convection problems
474 to develop intuition about the relevant fluid mechanics and plume behaviors. The 2d
475 model works best for purely thermal plumes without bubbles; rotating bubble plumes
476 have not yet been satisfactorily modeled using our 2d approach. Perhaps the greatest
477 surprise in the solutions is the importance of rotation to the eventual statistical steady
478 state. This tends to more effectively trap fluid in the vicinity of the wellhead and nurtures
479 the development of near field swirl speeds. Rotational plumes exhibit a strong tendency
480 to ascend upward off the plume central axis and can show downward velocities over the
481 wellhead.

482 The picture emerging from these studies differs from the classical non-rotating plume
483 models that have been applied to the DwH event (*Socolofsky et al.* [2011]) and the question
484 arises if the observations support one model type over the other. What is most clear from
485 the data is that a well-defined plume of Macondo hydrocarbon was found at roughly 1175m
486 depth, some 350m above the wellhead, and streamed primarily to the southwest from the
487 release site (*Camilli et al.* [2010], *McNutt et al.* [2012], *Reddy et al.* [2012], *Spier et al.*
488 [2013]). The thickness of the plume was between 100 and 200m and high hydrocarbon
489 concentrations were observed over a potential density range of $.06\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ (*Socolofsky et al.*
490 [2011]). At least three other shallower depths also exhibited evidences of plumes, but we
491 focus on the deepest one due to our interests in nearfield plume development. Trapping
492 depths like this have been predicted from the non-rotating models (*Socolofsky et al.* [2011]),
493 however, it is also possible to infer such behavior from the results reported here. We

494 have computed spreading heights from $130m$ to $600m$ depending on the stratification.
495 These heights emerge from our pure thermal plume, however trapping heights like this
496 have also been seen in our 3d DwH-like simulations. There is also some suggestion of
497 intrinsic variability in the rotating plumes. Whether the same occurs for the non-rotating
498 plumes is unclear, although it has not appeared in any of our computations. Intrinsic
499 plume penetration variability thus emerges as a possible contributor to the width both in
500 physical space and in density space of the high hydrocarbon observations.

501 The biggest distinctions in the structures of the rotating and non-rotating plumes occur
502 in the velocity fields around the plumes. Specifically, swirl velocities are absent from the
503 non-rotating plumes and the rotating plumes are much broader in near field diameter.

504 Observations that can comment on these details are somewhat sparse. *Camilli et al.*
505 [2012] report DwH plume velocity measurements within meters of the wellhead, but these
506 are focussed on vertical velocities, are only a few minutes in duration and were taken in
507 the transition between the failed 'Top Fill' confinement exercise and the commencement
508 of the 'Top Hat #4' placement. At that point, the release was confined to a single leak
509 by severing the connection to the open end 'Riser' about $250m$ from the DwH wellhead.
510 It is unclear how to interpret the results presented here in terms of these measurements
511 but it does seem the data mentioned above cannot discriminate between the predictions
512 of the non-rotating models and our rotating results.

513 One other interesting observational result also bears explicit mention. In an analysis of
514 all available quality controlled NOAA and BP hydrocarbon data, *Spier et al.* [2013] found
515 that the surface oil expression above the release site was roughly $1.6km$ in diameter, and
516 thus considerably broader than the $0.3km$ diameter surface footprint predicted by the

517 non-rotating models. Lateral enhancement of the near-field plume is a natural result of
518 the rotational dynamics in our model; a simple updrafting over the wellhead at a spreading
519 angle of roughly 0.1 is prevented by the adverse vertical pressure gradient. Instead, the
520 buoyant fluid is forced to escape laterally and spreads much more effectively in the near
521 field. As opposed to the non-rotating plume radii of $\sim 50m$ at the spreading level, we
522 routinely see plume radii in excess of $250m$ at the spreading level (see Fig. 7).

4.1. Future Work

523 While the literature supports the use of a single gas slip velocity to capture the multi-
524 phase nature of a bubble plume, our model allows the inclusion of more than one bubble
525 size, and hence more than one slip velocity. Numerical simulations are underway to ex-
526 amine the impact of this modification.

527 However, the most important factor not yet explored for rotating multiphase plume is
528 undoubtedly crossflow. The scale estimates presented in *Socolofsky et al.* [2011] suggest the
529 DwH event was more 'stratification' dominated than 'cross-flow' dominated. It remains to
530 determine how to distinguish between these two regimes for the case of rotating buoyant
531 point source releases. Our plans are to pursue such simulations, although this promises to
532 be a computationally demanding problem because of the need move beyond the economical
533 2d model and compute multiphase behaviors over a much larger area. However, it is
534 possible that lessons from the symmetric simulations can be imported to the cross-flow
535 problem in the manner that they have been for non-rotating plumes (*Zheng et al.* [2003]).

Appendix A: A Multiphase Model for Deep Water Oil Spills

536 Multiphase flows are well known in the engineering community, but less so among
 537 oceanographers. We therefore present here a development of the equations for two phases
 538 of liquid and one phase of gas along with a discussion of the errors and approximations.

539 The equations governing each phase of the mixture are the stratified Navier-Stokes equa-
 540 tions, consisting of mass, momentum and energy equations, along with tracer equations
 541 related to fluid or gas density by an equation of state.

The momentum equations are

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{u}_i) + \mathbf{f} \times \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i + \nabla \pi_i + \nabla \cdot \mathbb{F}_i^{(x)} = 0 \quad (\text{A1})$$

where the subscript i denotes a particular mixture constituent, π_i denotes pressure and $\mathbb{F}_i^{(k)}$ denotes the viscous fluxes in the k direction. The quantities $f = 2\Omega \sin \theta$, $\tilde{f} = 2\Omega \cos \theta$ are the Coriolis parameters with the former the more familiar, vertical one, and other notation is standard. We keep both Coriolis components in view of the relatively weak stratification of the deep ocean and the recognized effects of full rotation on convection in the mid and equatorial latitudes (*Sheremet* [2004]). The mass equations can be written as

$$\rho_{it} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i) = 0 \quad (\text{A2})$$

where we ignore biological and chemical degradation of oil and gas, and the tracer equations as

$$(\rho_i T_i)_t + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i T_i) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}_{T_i} = 0, \quad (\text{A3})$$

where \mathbf{F}_{T_i} represents the diffusive flux of property T_i . Tracers and density are linked via equations of state of the form

$$\rho_i = \rho_i(T_i, p_i), \quad (\text{A4})$$

542 where there can be more than one tracer, T_i , involved in the equation of state (e.g.
543 temperature and salinity for seawater).

All of the prognostic equations involve a so-called 'conservative' operator of the form

$$\mathbb{Z}(p_i) = (\rho_i p_i)_t + \nabla \Psi_{P_i}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

where Ψ_{P_i} is a generalized flux of property p_i . For example, the generalized flux of the tracer T_i is

$$\Psi_{T_i} = \mathbf{u} \rho_i T_i + \mathbf{F}_{T_i} \quad (\text{A6})$$

544 and consists of both advective and non-advective parts.

The equations governing the evolution of constituent i do not apply everywhere in space. Rather, they are limited in their influence to domains where constituent i is found; interactions between the constituents occur at interfaces that separate the various constituent domains. To write globally valid equations then, it is necessary to multiply each of the above equations by a variant of the Heaviside step function, here denoted by $H_i(\mathbf{x})$, ($H_i(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ if constituent i is found at location; $H_i(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ otherwise) and sum them. Thus, for example, the general form of the east west momentum equation becomes

$$\sum_i H_i \left[(\rho_i u_i)_t + \nabla(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i u_i) - f \rho_i v_i + \tilde{f} \rho_i w_i + \pi_{ix} + \nabla \mathbb{F}_i^{(x)} \right] = 0 \quad (\text{A7})$$

545 which is valid at every point in space.

We now apply an integral approach where the general equations will be integrated over a fixed volume and budgets for each of the properties developed. A helpful first demonstration of this procedure follows from volume integrating the conservative operator in (A5)

$$I_p = \int_{V_p} \left[\sum_i H_i [(\rho_i p_i)_t + \nabla \Psi_{P_i}] \right] dV = \sum_i \int_{V_i} [H_i [(\rho_i p_i)_t + \nabla \Psi_{P_i}]] dV_i. \quad (\text{A8})$$

546 In the first integration, the quantity V_p denotes a volume centered on a fixed location
 547 where we wish to know how a bulk dynamic quantity p (e.g. volume averaged density or
 548 momentum) will evolve. On the right hand side of (A8), the volumes V_i are restricted
 549 to the regions inhabited by constituent i inside V_p . The surfaces bounding V_i are of two
 550 types. They are either interfaces within the larger volume V_p , or they are surfaces on
 551 the bounding faces of V_p wholly encircled by an interface separating i from some other
 552 constituent (a two dimensional example appears in Fig. 10). The behaviors of these two
 553 surfaces are fundamentally different, with the former free to move within V_p and the latter
 554 constrained to lie on a surface fixed in space.

For a two-dimensional case, (A8) becomes

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_1} \int_{z_0}^{z_1} \left[\sum_i H_i [(\rho_i p_i)_t + (\Psi_{pi})_x + (\Psi_{pi})_z] \right] dz dx = \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$\sum_i \int_{x_0}^{x_+} \int_{z_-}^{z_+} [(\rho_i p_i)_t + (\Psi_{pi})_x + (\Psi_{pi})_z] dz dx$$

and consider the single integral over constituent i (shown as grey in Fig. 10). The last integral is trivial to perform. Pulling the derivatives out of the integrations in the first two right hand side terms and recalling that the interface inside V_p can move returns

$$I_{p_i} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{x_o}^{x_+} \int_{z_-}^{z_+} \rho_i p_i dz dx + \int_{x_o}^{x_+} (\rho_i p_i z_t^+ - \Psi_{p_i} \cdot (\mathbf{k} - z_x^+ \mathbf{i})) dx \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$\underline{- \int_{x_0}^{x_+} (\rho_i p_i z_t^- - \Psi_{p_i} \cdot (\mathbf{k} - z_x^- \mathbf{i})) dx} + \int_{z_o^-}^{z_o^+} \Psi_{p_i} dz$$

The underlined terms vanish upon the summation because they represent exchanges entirely within V_p . For example, if $p = 1$ (we consider mass), the underlined terms take the form

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_+} \rho_i (z_t^+ - u_i z_i x + w_i) dx = 0, \quad (\text{A11})$$

which vanishes due to the immiscibility of the fluids. A similar result holds for all properties, p . The remaining non-advective fluxes are due to viscous or diffusive effects. These are incapable of producing momentum, mass or heat (neglecting the viscous heat of dissipation) and so will simply redistribute these properties between constituents within the fixed volume. Thus the intuitively pleasing result is found that the bulk change of property p within the volume element caused by conservative processes is wholly controlled by the generalized multiphase flux of p through the fixed boundaries of the domain

$$\sum_i I_{pi} = \sum_i \left[\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V_i} \rho_i p_i dA_i + \oint_{\partial V_{pi}} \Psi_{pi} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p dl_i \right]. \quad (\text{A12})$$

555 This argument is easily generalized to three dimensions.

An analogous procedure can be applied to the pressure gradients in the momentum equations. In principle the pressures across interfaces can differ due to processes like surface tension. For the present oceanographic application these will be ignored. Applying continuity of pressure at interfaces within V_p thus yields

$$\sum_i \int_{V_i} \nabla p_i dV_i = \int_{S_p} p \mathbf{n} dS_p, \quad (\text{A13})$$

556 where the continuity of pressure has allowed the removal of the constituent subscript.

557 The only remaining momentum quantities are the Coriolis accelerations, which are
558 straightforward to integrate, thus completing the volume-based discretization of (A1). To
559 this point, the only approximations that have been made are the neglect of surface physics
560 associated with the contact between the fluid constituents at their interfaces.

We now introduce the more important approximations. Consider first the form of the integrated mass equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_i \int_{V_{pi}} \rho_i dV_i + \sum_i \int_{S_i} \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \mathbf{n} dS_i = 0. \quad (\text{A14})$$

The net mass in the mass control volume has contributions from oil(s), water and gas(es), the densities of which are greatly different. Water density is roughly 1035kg m^{-3} in the deep ocean, oil is at most about 840kg m^{-3} and at 150 atmospheres, methane is roughly 100kg m^{-3} . If we adopt a density scale of

$$\rho_0 = \frac{\rho_{oil} + \rho_{water}}{2} = 937\text{kg m}^{-3} \quad (\text{A15})$$

water and oil density variability relative to ρ_0 is about 10%, while the full gas density is only about 10% of ρ_0 . Often in such models, the bubble mass is neglected, i.e. the bubbles are modelled as 'voids'. We adopt this approximation. Considering the extreme case of a volume of half gas and half oil, the volume average density is 460kg m^{-3} , as compared to the approximate density estimate of 425kg m^{-3} obtained by entirely neglecting the gas. The error, more than 10% here, will be smaller for other less extreme settings. Neglecting gas density, the mass equation becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \int_{V_{pi}} \rho_i dV_i + \sum_{i \neq i_g} \int_{S_{pi}} \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \mathbf{n} dS_i = 0 \quad (\text{A16})$$

where i_g denotes indices reserved for gases. To simplify (A16) further, we write

$$\int_{V_{pi}} \rho_i dV_i = \overline{\rho}_i \delta V_i; \quad \int_{S_{pi}} \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \mathbf{n} dS_i = \overline{\mathbf{u}_i \rho}_i \delta S_i, \quad (\text{A17})$$

where the overbar denotes either a volume average over the constituent volume or a surface average over a constituent surface on the cell volume boundary. Which definition applies will be clear by context. Dividing (A17) by the cell volume

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \overline{\rho}_i \alpha_i + \sum_{i \neq i_g} \frac{1}{\delta} \overline{\mathbf{u}_i \rho}_i^j f_i^j = 0, \quad (\text{A18})$$

where α_i denotes the volume fraction of i in volume V_p , the index j marks the faces of the cell and f_i^j the surface fraction of the same constituent on the surface j bounding the

volume. The quantity δ dividing the surface integrals represents the left over dimension of the cell volume. For example, the bulk zonal divergence of the mass flux becomes

$$\frac{1}{V_{pi}} \int_{S_{pi}} [u_i \rho_i(x^+) - u_i \rho_i(x^-)] dydz = \frac{\overline{u_i \rho_i(x^+) f_i^+} - \overline{u_i \rho_i(x^-) f_i^-}}{\delta_x}. \quad (\text{A19})$$

561 Clearly, to integrate ahead in time, exchanges between neighboring cells must be ex-
 562 pressed in terms of known quantities, i.e. the volume averaged mean quantities. This is
 563 the parameterization problem of multiphase fluids expressed in the context of the mass
 564 equation and is representative of the artistry in multiphase modelling.

It is convenient at this point to compute also the budget V_p in of the mass of a single constituent. This reduces to the volume integration of a purely conservative quantity over a single index i . Further, the generalized flux of the mass consists only of an advective contribution and the fluids are immiscible. The result for a single constituent is

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\overline{\rho_i \alpha_i}) + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_j \overline{\mathbf{u}_i \rho_i^j f_i^j} = 0. \quad (\text{A20})$$

We now introduce a second simplification. We treat the mixture fluids as individually Boussinesq and collectively Boussinesq. The former constraint assumes

$$\frac{\delta \rho_{oil}}{\rho_{oil}} \ll 1; \quad \frac{\delta \rho_{water}}{\rho_{water}} \ll 1, \quad (\text{A21})$$

both of which are familiar approximations. The 'collectively Boussinesq' assumption requires the stronger and less justifiable assertion that

$$\frac{\rho_{oil} - \rho_0}{\rho_0} \sim \frac{\rho_{water} - \rho_0}{\rho_0} \ll 1. \quad (\text{A22})$$

The error introduced by the assumption inherent in (A22) is about 10%. Although less justifiable than for single-phase water, 10% compares well to the order of approximation in (A16). If the above approximations are accepted, then the budget for mass of constituent

i , where the index does not include gas, becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt}\alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_j \overline{\mathbf{u}_i^j} f_i^j = O\left(\frac{\rho_i - \rho_0}{\rho_0}\right) \ll 1, \quad (\text{A23})$$

while the total mass budget for the cell becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbf{u}_i^j} f_i^j = O\left(\frac{\rho_i - \rho_0}{\rho_0}\right) \ll 1. \quad (\text{A24})$$

It will also be necessary for momentum reasons to monitor the mass of gas in a cell, the equation for which can be obtained by integration. The result is

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\overline{\rho_g} \alpha_g) + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_j \overline{\mathbf{u}_g \rho_g^j} f_g^j = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} M_g + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_j \overline{\mathbf{u}_g \rho_g^j} f_g^j \quad (\text{A25})$$

where M_g mass per unit volume of gas. The gas density can be expected to vary given the strong pressure differences encountered during an ascent. Approximating the pressure by the static value of $p = \rho_0 g z$, the ideal gas law can be used to compute the gas density via

$$\frac{\rho_0 g z}{RT} = \overline{\rho_g}. \quad (\text{A26})$$

565 Elaborations based on more accurate equations of state are also available. Computing M_g
566 and dividing by ρ_g provides a prediction of α_g .

We now move to the momentum equations, the north-south one being

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_i \overline{(\rho_i v_i)} \alpha_i + f \sum_i \overline{(\rho_i u_i)} \alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i,j} \overline{(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i v_i)^j} f_i^j + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i,j} \overline{\mathbb{F}_i^{(y)j}} f_i^j + \frac{\delta p}{\delta y} = 0 \quad (\text{A27})$$

The handling of the zonal momentum equation will mirror this, while the vertical momentum equation must be handled separately, as is typical for the Boussinesq equations.

We again neglect the gases due to their small mass, which amounts to restricting (A27) to not include the gas indices. The term

$$\frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i,j} \overline{\mathbb{F}_i^{(y)j}} f_i^j \quad (\text{A28})$$

denotes the aggregate impact of viscous effects and reduces to only those contributions occurring on the cell interfaces. This results from the requirement that all internal viscous exchanges between the liquids conserve momentum and the approximation that gas momentum is negligible. The use of the extended Boussinesq approximation in (A27) allows it to be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \bar{v}_i \alpha_i + f \sum_{i \neq i_g} \bar{u}_i \alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \bar{\mathbf{u}}_i v_i^j f_i^j + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbb{F}_i^{(y)^j}} f_i^j = O\left(\frac{\rho_{oi} - \rho_0}{\rho_0}\right) \ll 1, \quad (\text{A29})$$

567 where the reference oil and water densities are denoted by ρ_{oi} . Assuming adequate data
 568 is available at one time level, the result of applying (A29) is a prediction for the oil and
 569 water volume weighted velocity (hereafter the composite velocity) associated with a point
 570 at the center of the V_v volume.

We now consider the volume averaged vertical momentum equation. Singling out the buoyancy and pressure terms,

$$-\frac{\delta p}{\delta z} - \sum_i \bar{\rho}_i g \alpha_i. \quad (\text{A30})$$

the usual procedure of removing the static pressure contribution returns

$$-\frac{\delta \hat{p}}{\delta z} - \sum_i (\bar{\rho}_i - \rho_0) g \alpha_i, \quad (\text{A31})$$

571 where \hat{p} is the modified pressure (we will drop the hat in the following).

Following normal Boussinesq procedure, the density variations for the oil and water will be retained when multiplied by gravity. Note however that the gas produces a potentially huge contribution to the buoyancy due to its large mass deficit. Thus, while we can safely neglect the contribution of gas to momentum in any direction and to the mass of a cell, it cannot be neglected with regards to buoyancy forcing. Dividing the vertical momentum equation by the reference density, and neglecting the mass of the gas, the

vertical momentum equation becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \overline{w_i} \alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbf{u}_i w_i^j} f_i^j - \tilde{f} \sum_{i \neq i_g} \overline{u_i} \alpha_i + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbb{F}_i^{(z)j}} f_i^j - \sum_i \overline{b_i} = 0, \quad (\text{A32})$$

with

$$\overline{b_i} = -g \frac{\overline{\rho_i} - \rho_0}{\rho_0}. \quad (\text{A33})$$

To this point, the substantive assumptions we have made are the extended Boussinesq character of the flows and the neglect of gas in computing cell mass and cell momentum. We could push further with this set, but it is useful and relatively benign to introduce another restriction. The gas will be assumed to be dilute, i.e. $\alpha_g \ll 1$. Admittedly, the initial DwH gas volume fraction was not small, but our calculations show it disperses quickly. Realistic net void fluxes can still be included into the problem by spreading the bubble flux over a large area. The value of neglecting the gas void fraction is that it avoids having to consider compression. In the mass equation (A23) since $\alpha_g \ll 1$ the first term is comparable to the error and can be neglected

$$\alpha_{oil} + \alpha_{water} = 1 - O(\alpha_{gas}) \sim 1. \quad (\text{A34})$$

The composite mass thus behaves like that of an incompressible fluid

$$\frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbf{u}_i^j} f_i^j = 0. \quad (\text{A35})$$

572 Now we consider the question of how to advance the model one-time step. For numerical
 573 calculations, the normal C-grid structure for the model lattice, with mass points at the
 574 center of a cube between meridional velocity points to the north and south, zonal velocity
 575 points to the east and west and vertical velocity points above and below, works well. The
 576 mass points are also the locations of tracer and volume fraction data. The cells around

577 the velocity points are similarly defined. This is useful as many ocean models adopt C
578 grid structure.

579 We assume gas volume fraction and one of the oil/water volume fractions and the
580 oil and water velocities are known at some time level. From these and using (A34)
581 we can construct the composite velocity field. Recalling (A35), a diagnostic equation
582 involving a discrete analog of the Laplacian of the pressure can be formed. With surface
583 exchanges expressed in terms of volume averages, the equation is closed and pressure
584 can be computed. The composite momentum equations can now be integrated in time.
585 The tracer and volume fraction equations are integrated with the assumption of fixed slip
586 velocities in the vertical although this is not necessary. This essentially completes the
587 discrete equation set.

A1. Conversion to Partial Differential Equations

The multiphase equations derived above are in a form that lends itself to numerical computation. Our fluid mechanical intuition is more deeply rooted in partial differential equations, i.e. in the continuum limit. We here perform the conversion to PDEs adopting along the way suitable parameterizations for the exchanges between cells. We associate the volume averaged velocity and net buoyancy with the notation

$$\mathbf{U} = \sum_{i \neq i_g} \mathbf{u}_i \alpha_i, \quad B = -g \sum_{i \neq i_g} \frac{\rho_i - \rho_0}{\rho_0} \alpha_i - g \alpha_g. \quad (\text{A36})$$

To write the momentum equations, we need to parameterize the advective and diffusive momentum exchanges at the cell interface. Perhaps the simplest advective parameterization is

$$\sum_{i \neq i_g, j} \overline{\mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{u}_i^j} f_i^j = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{U} \mathbf{U}) \quad (\text{A37})$$

which is equivalent to approximating momentum flux at the interface by using averages of the composite velocities. Doing essentially the same for the diffusive transfers yields the mixture momentum equations

$$\mathbf{U}_t + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}\mathbf{U} + \mathbf{f} \times \mathbf{U} = -\nabla p + B\mathbf{k} + \nabla \cdot D_U \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U}, \quad (\text{A38})$$

where D_U is a tensor controlling the amplitude of the diffusive fluxes. It is then consistent to write (A35) as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0. \quad (\text{A39})$$

The tracer equations become

$$T_t + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}T = \nabla \cdot D_t \cdot \nabla T. \quad (\text{A40})$$

The distinctions between these equations and regular Navier-Stokes arises in the volume fraction equations, which are

$$\alpha_{it} + \nabla \cdot ((\mathbf{U} + w_i\mathbf{k})\alpha_i) = \nabla \cdot D_\alpha \cdot \nabla \alpha_i, \quad (\text{A41})$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} M_g + \nabla \cdot ((\mathbf{U} + w_g\mathbf{k})M_g) = \nabla \cdot D_\alpha \cdot \nabla M_g, \quad (\text{A42})$$

with the additional constraint

$$\sum_{i \neq i_g} \alpha_i = 1 \quad (\text{A43})$$

588 M_g is the mass distribution of the gas, given by $M_g = \bar{\rho}_g \alpha_g$ with gas density set nominally
 589 by the ideal gas law (A26). The flux tensors for material X , D_X , must be parameterized
 590 in terms of the modelled variables and chemical/biological effects can appear on the right
 591 hand sides of the volume fraction equations.

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Figure 1. Snapshot of the plume after 10h. Blue is bubble concentration, gray is oil concentration and color is temperature difference from the bottom temperature.

Figure 2. Average radial and vertical velocity (shown as vectors) and azimuthal velocity (shown in color; blue is anticyclonic circulation, red is cyclonic).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	DwH	Units
Inlet diameter	D	0.08	0.4	m
Slip velocity	w_s	0.016	0.20	m s^{-1}
Stratification	ζ	5.1	$\sim .004$	K m^{-1}
Height of the domain	H	2.66	1500	m
Radius of the domain	R	2.66	∞	m
Gravity acceleration	g	9.8	9.8	m s^2
Inlet temperature	$T(z = 0)$	12.7	100	C
Inlet gas volume fraction	$\alpha_{gas,0}$	0.00254	0.5	-
Inlet liquid phase velocity	w_0	0.04	2.0	m s^{-1}
Inlet buoyancy flux	B_0	5×10^{-6}	1.4	$\text{m}^4 \text{s}^{-3}$
Coriolis parameter	f	0.01	$\sim .4 \times 10^{-4}$	s^{-1}
Stratification frequency	N	0.1	$\sim 4 \times 10^{-4}$	s^{-1}
Reynolds number	Re	7071	$\sim 10^6$	-
Richardson number	Ri	3685	8.5×10^4	-
Péclet number	Pe	7071	$\sim 10^6$	-
Rossby number	Ro	10	~ 15	-

Table 1. Parameters for the 2d-3d comparison runs. The fourth column contains DwH parameters.

Figure 3. Mean vertical velocity comparisons between 2d and 3d simulations. The left two panels are pure thermal plumes ($f_T = 1$) and the right two panels are hybrid plumes with one half of the buoyancy flux from thermal and bubble sources, respectively ($f_b = f_T = 0.5$). The upper panels are non-rotating ($Ro = \infty$) and the lower panels rotating ($Ro = 10$). Distances are non-dimensionalized by the scale $0.266m$. The velocities, shown in color, are non-dimensionalized by $0.0266m/s$.

Figure 4. Same as Fig. 3, but for radial velocity.

Figure 5. Comparison of the vertical structure of mean centerline vertical velocity, temperature and gas volume fraction. $Ro = \infty$ (left) and $Ro = 10$ (right) with 3D results solid and 2D results dashed. Thermal plumes are in red and hybrid, thermal-bubble plumes in blue.

Figure 6. Left: Radial profiles of the mean vertical velocity at $z = 3$ for the rotating and non-rotating thermal and hybrid plumes. Right: Vertical profiles of the volume flux, Q . 3D results in solid lines, 2D results dashed.

Figure 7. Streamfunction (left) and passive scalar (right) at $Ro = \infty$ ($N = 4.5 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ and $f = 0$) (top), $Ro = 45$ ($N = 4.5 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ and $f = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$) (middle) and $Ro = 10$ ($N = 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ and $f = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$) (bottom) at $t = 5$ days.

Figure 8. The structure of the strongly stratified and strongly rotating plume oscillation as it appears in temperature. Twenty minutes separates each plot.

Figure 9. As Fig. 8, but for angular momentum, which is approximately a materially conserved quantity. The bottom right plot is of a passive tracer at day 5.

Figure 10. Two-dimensional grid schematic with three constituents denoted by i , j , and k . The east-west (δx) and vertical (δz) dimensions of the cell are shown and the center domain point is indicated by the large dark dot. The shaded area is the sub-domain of constituent i (V_i), the blue areas are constituent j and both are embedded within a cell otherwise full of constituent k . The full square is the domain V_p over which the integration is carried out. The interior interfaces between constituents i and k are denoted by $z^+(x)$ and $z^-(x)$ and extends from the fixed grid boundary at $x = x_1$ to the interior point x^+ . The intersections of the grey interface with the grid boundary are denoted by z_o^- and z_o^+ .

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